

Principals' Soft Skills and Management Efficiency in Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between principals' soft skills and management efficiency in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Five research questions guided the study and five null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. From a population of 6, 899 a sample of 268 teachers was drawn using proportionate stratified- random sampling technique. Two questionnaires titled "Principals' Soft Skill Questionnaire (PSSQ) and School Management Efficiency Questionnaire (SMEQ)" were used to collect data for the study. The instruments were validated by two experts from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and one expert from the Department of Educational Foundation (Measurement and Evaluation) all in the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Internal consistency of the instruments was determined using Cronbach's Alpha method and coefficients of 0.84 and 0.85 were obtained for the two instruments PSSQ and SMEQ respectively. Data were analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis. P-value was used to determine the significance of correlation at 0.05 significant level. The findings revealed that principals interpersonal, leadership, adaptability, decision-making and resilience skills all had significant positive relationships with management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. The study concluded that principals' soft skills are critical determinants of effective and efficient school management. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school principals should be regularly trained and retrained through workshops, seminars and leadership development programmes to enhance their soft skills for improved school management efficiency.

Keywords: Principals, Soft Skills, Management, Management Efficiency

Introduction:

Education is widely recognized as a fundamental instrument for national development, social transformation, and the promotion of human capital (Akinola, 2022). In Nigeria, the education system is structured into three main levels: primary, secondary, and tertiary education, with each level serving a distinct purpose in the development of learners and the nation as a whole (Federal Ministry of Education (FME), 2013). The Nigerian education system is governed by

policies that aim to ensure access, equity, quality, and relevance of education, guided by the National Policy on Education (NPE, 2019). At the foundational level, primary education provides basic literacy and numeracy skills and serves as the entry point for formal learning. This is followed by secondary education, which is intended to consolidate foundational knowledge, prepare students for higher education or vocational training, and equip them with critical thinking, problem-solving, and social skills necessary for personal and national development (Okeke and Ugwoke, 2021).

Secondary education in Nigeria serves as the critical bridge between foundational primary education and higher academic or vocational pursuits. According to the National Policy on Education (FME, 2013), secondary education is the level of education that bridges the gap between primary and tertiary education. The objectives of secondary education are designed to provide adequate preparation for higher education, vocational training and lifelong learning. Specifically, secondary education aims to provide students with the knowledge and skills necessary for further education, equip them with practical and technical competencies for employment or self-reliance and promote the all-round development of the individual intellectually, morally, socially and physically. It also seeks to instill a sense of civic responsibility, national consciousness and social awareness, prepare students for adult life and informed career choices, foster an appreciation for science, technology, and cultural heritage, and lay the foundation for lifelong learning and personal growth.

However, achieving these goals goes beyond mere curriculum delivery, it requires strategic and efficient management. This means that the success of secondary schools depends on well-coordinated policies, resource optimization, and a supportive learning environment that nurtures well-rounded individuals ready to contribute meaningfully to society. Managing a secondary school is a multifaceted endeavour that blends administrative precision with human-centered leadership. Weihrich, Cannice and Koontz (2019) defined management as the process of designing and maintaining an environment in which individuals, working together in groups, efficiently accomplish selected aims. Griffin (2025) explained that management is a set of activities directed at an organization's resources, with the aim of achieving organizational goals in an efficient and effective manner. This definition recognizes management as an active and dynamic process. Operationally, management is defined as the strategic and systematic coordination of human, material and financial resources by secondary school principals to ensure the effective administration of schools, enhance teaching and learning outcomes and promote overall management efficiency. In the context of this study, management refers to the process by which school principals plan, organize, coordinate, direct and control the activities of a secondary school to achieve its educational goals effectively and efficiently. It involves the optimal use of human, financial, and material resources, supervision of staff, facilitation of teaching and learning, maintenance of discipline and engagement with stakeholders to ensure that school objectives are met.

In schools, management efficiency is about creating ecosystems where policies transform into student success, and where every resource is leveraged to fulfill the National Policy on Education's promises. According to Ogbonnaya (2019), management efficiency encompasses strategic planning, resource allocation, staff supervision, student discipline, and community engagement. It is a balancing act where policies meet practicality, and where the principal's ability to inspire, organize, and innovate determines institutional success. In the context of this study, management efficiency in secondary schools refers to the effective coordination and utilization of human, material and financial resources to achieve educational objectives. Efficient management ensures that schools operate smoothly, fostering an environment conducive to teaching and learning. Key indicators of management efficiency include optimal resource allocation, staff motivation, student academic performance and minimal wastage of resources.

In Anambra State, where educational standards are highly prioritized, the efficiency of school management can mean the difference between mediocrity and excellence (Nwankwo, 2022). Nwankwo buttressed that a well-managed school ensures: (i) optimal use of financial and material resources; (ii) high teacher morale and productivity; (iii) improved student academic performance, and; (iv) a positive school-community relationship. Despite Anambra State having a strong cultural emphasis on academic excellence, the efficiency of school management remains inconsistent across its secondary schools. One of the most pressing issues is the inadequate supervision and leadership inefficiency among school administrators. Many principals lack the necessary managerial skills to coordinate school activities effectively (Nwaelehia, Woken and Orji, 2024). Decision-making is often delayed or inconsistent due to bureaucratic bottlenecks, leading to poor implementation of policies. The inability to enforce discipline among teachers and students also contributes to a decline in academic standards as a result of poor resource management.

Poor resource management is another major concern. Funds allocated for school projects and maintenance are frequently mismanaged or insufficiently utilized. Many public schools struggle with inadequate classroom space, outdated teaching materials, and poor sanitation facilities, making the learning environment unconducive (Umeghalu and Obi 2020). In some cases, essential school resources are diverted for personal gains, exacerbating the issue of inefficiency. Amidst the widespread inefficiencies plaguing public secondary schools in Anambra State, the role of principals' soft skills has become increasingly crucial in fostering management efficiency. While technical knowledge and administrative experience are essential, a principal's ability to communicate effectively, lead with emotional intelligence, manage conflicts and foster teamwork significantly impacts the overall functionality of a school.

For school principals, skills are essential for ensuring efficiency in administration, communication, decision-making, and conflict resolution all of which contribute to effective school management. According to Kamalu and Mbakwe (2022), skills refer to the abilities, competencies, and expertise that enable individuals to perform tasks effectively, solve problems,

and achieve organizational goals. Robles (2020) defined skill as a learned capacity to carry out a function with determined results, often within a given amount of time, energy, or both. Skills are broadly categorized into hard skills and soft skills. While both play a role in school management, soft skills are particularly crucial for principals in ensuring leadership effectiveness.

Soft skills refer to personal, emotional, and social abilities that determine how individuals interact, communicate, and collaborate with others. Unlike hard skills, which focus on technical competencies, soft skills shape a leader's ability to inspire, motivate, and manage people effectively (Gertrude, Ahiwe and Obinna 2023). In the context of secondary school management, soft skills enable principals to foster a positive school culture, build trust among teachers and students, resolve conflicts, and drive innovation. As schools are dynamic institutions with multiple stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and policymakers, principals require strong interpersonal and leadership skills to navigate complex challenges effectively. Studies of Kamalu and Mbakwe (2022) and Gertrude, Ahiwe and Obinna (2023) highlighted the following dimensions of soft skills: emotional intelligence, problem-solving skills, communication skills, interpersonal skills, leadership skills, adaptability skills, decision-making skills, resilience skills, stress management skills, creativity, team-building skills and critical thinking skills. But for the purpose of this study, attention will be focused on three highly important skills which are interpersonal skills, leadership skills and adaptability skills. This is because these skills have direct relevance to the role of principals in ensuring management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Interpersonal skills refer to a principal's ability to communicate, collaborate, and build relationships with teachers, students, parents, and the community. A principal with strong interpersonal skills fosters a positive school culture, promotes teamwork, and enhances staff morale. Such a leader listens actively, resolves conflicts effectively, and maintains open lines of communication, ensuring that all stakeholders work towards common goals (Northouse, 2019). Conversely, a principal who lacks interpersonal skills may struggle to build trust, leading to misunderstandings, low staff motivation, and resistance to policies, which ultimately hampers school management.

Building upon interpersonal abilities, leadership skills enable principals to inspire and guide their schools toward achieving academic excellence and institutional goals. Effective leaders set clear visions, motivate staff, and make strategic decisions that enhance school operations. A principal with strong leadership skills nurtures a collaborative environment, empowering teachers and students to perform at their best. They also encourage professional development and innovation, ensuring the school remains competitive and efficient. Without strong leadership skills, principals may struggle to establish authority, resulting in poor staff performance, disorganization, and an overall decline in educational standards (Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, 2020).

Adaptability refers to the capacity to adjust one's thinking, behaviour, and strategies in response to new, changing, or unexpected conditions (Martin, Nejad, Colmar and Liem, 2020).

The dynamic nature of education demands that principals embrace new teaching methods, technology, and administrative reforms. Principals with high adaptability skills can navigate unforeseen challenges, such as curriculum adjustments or crises like the COVID-19 pandemic, ensuring minimal disruptions to learning (Nurhattati, Rahmawati, Rugaiyah, Ripki, and Wicaksono, 2023). On the other hand, a rigid principal who resists change may hinder innovation, causing stagnation and inefficiency in school operations. Such resistance can lead to outdated teaching practices, staff frustration, and a decline in students' academic performance.

When these soft skills are present, principals can foster a collaborative, innovative, and supportive school environment that enhances teaching and learning outcomes. In Anambra State, where secondary schools still face diverse challenges including inadequate funding, staff turnover, student discipline issues, and curriculum reforms principals' ability to lead effectively hinges on their soft skills. Currently, many principals in Anambra State ascend to leadership positions based on tenure, academic qualifications, or political influences rather than leadership competencies. Studies suggest that while some principals possess technical expertise, they lack the soft skills necessary for efficient school administration (Olayemi, 2023). For instance, principals with weak interpersonal skills may struggle to build team cohesion among teachers, leading to low morale and reduced instructional effectiveness.

Similarly, those lacking adaptability skills may resist modern teaching methodologies and technological advancements, limiting students' exposure to innovative learning experiences (Hallinger and Heck, 2021). Schools where principals demonstrate poor leadership and interpersonal skills may often experience frequent conflicts, declining teacher commitment, and reduced academic performance (Leithwood, *et al.*, 2020). Personal observation of researcher in secondary schools in Anambra State suggests persistent managerial challenges. Despite the state's investment in education and its national recognition as one of the academically advanced states in the country, several schools in the state continue to experience inadequate instructional materials, weak maintenance culture, low staff morale, poor communication patterns, and inefficiencies in administrative processes. These issues raise concerns about principals' possession of necessary soft skills for managerial efficiency. This is because effective leadership extends beyond technical knowledge and administrative procedures. A principal may possess professional qualifications and managerial experience yet struggle to achieve optimal outcomes without strong soft skills that enable effective communication, collaboration, teacher empowerment and the capacity to adjust one's behaviour. It is against this background that this study examined the principals' soft skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Effective management of secondary schools depends not only on technical and administrative competence but also on the quality of interpersonal and intrapersonal abilities demonstrated by school leaders. Principals, as chief administrators and instructional leaders, are

expected to possess essential soft skills such as communication, emotional intelligence, interpersonal relations, adaptability, teamwork, and conflict management. These skills influence how they relate with teachers, students, parents, and other stakeholders, and how effectively they coordinate human and material resources toward achieving school goals. Ideally, when principals demonstrate strong soft skills, they foster a positive school climate, enhance staff motivation, strengthen collaboration, and ultimately improve overall management efficiency.

However, personal observation of researchers in secondary schools in Anambra State suggests persistent managerial challenges. Despite the state's investment in education and its national recognition as one of the academically advanced states in the country, several schools continue to experience inadequate instructional materials, weak maintenance culture, low staff morale, poor communication patterns, and inefficiencies in administrative processes. These issues raise concerns about the effectiveness of school management at the secondary level.

While inadequate funding and systemic constraints may contribute to these challenges, it has been argued that effective leadership extends beyond technical knowledge and administrative procedures. A principal may possess professional qualifications and managerial experience yet struggle to achieve optimal outcomes without strong soft skills that enable effective communication, emotional regulation, collaboration, and conflict resolution. In many instances, recruitment, training, and performance evaluation systems for principals in Nigeria appear to emphasize academic credentials and years of service, with limited attention to soft skill competencies.

Furthermore, empirical studies in Nigeria have largely focused on principals' administrative competence, leadership styles, or resource management practices, with relatively limited attention given to the specific role of soft skills in enhancing management efficiency. In Anambra State particularly, there is insufficient empirical evidence establishing whether and to what extent principals' soft skills relate to their management efficiency.

This gap in knowledge makes it difficult to determine whether observed management inefficiencies are primarily associated with deficiencies in soft skills or are mainly the result of structural and contextual factors. Consequently, there is a need to investigate the relationship between principals' soft skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between principals' soft skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the relationship between:

1. principals' interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. principals' leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between principals' interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between principals' leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between principals' interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between principals' leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. There is no significant relationship between principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

The study adopted correlational research design. The study was conducted in the 268 public secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample of 719 teachers drawn using stratified random sampling technique was used for the study. Two instruments developed by the researchers were used for data collection namely: "Principals' Soft Skill Questionnaire (PSSQ) and "School Management Efficiency Questionnaire (SMEQ)". The instruments were validated by three lecturers; two in Department of Educational Management and one in Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation Unit), all from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Internal consistency coefficient of 0.83, 0.81 and 0.82 were obtained for PSSQ while 0.85 was obtained for SMEQ using Cronbach's Alpha statistical method. On the spot delivery method was used by the researchers and five research assistants to administer copies of the instrument to principals in their respective schools. At the end of the exercise, 59 copies (8.2%) were either lost or not properly filled and could not be used for the analysis. Only 619 copies out of the 660 copies administered were properly filled and retrieved and thus were used for data analysis. The return rate was approximately 91.8% of the sample which the researcher considered satisfactory for the study. Data obtained for the study were analyzed using Pearson's correlation analysis. the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient recommended by Nworgu (2015), as follows: .00- .19= Negligible Correlation; .20- .39= Low Correlation; .40- .59= Moderate Correlation; .60- .79=High

Correlation; .80- 1.00= Very High Relationship. For the null hypotheses, p-value was used to determine the significance of the correlation. Where the calculated p-value is less than the stipulated level of significance 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Whereas the null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated p-value is greater than the stipulated level of significance 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between principals’ interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson r on the Correlation between Principals’ Interpersonal Skills and Management Efficiency

Source of Variation	N	r	Remark
Interpersonal Skills	619	0.71	High Relationship
Management Efficiency			

Table 1 shows that there is a high positive relationship existing between principals’ interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is evident by the size of the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient r, which is 0.71. this suggests that as principals’ interpersonal skills increase, management efficiency in secondary schools also improves.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between principals’ leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson r on the Correlation between Principals’ Leadership Skills and Management Efficiency

Source of Variation	N	r	Remark
Leadership Skills	619	0.76	High Relationship
Management Efficiency			

Table 2 shows that the Pearson’s r = 0.76, indicating a high positive relationship between principals’ leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. This suggests that as principals’ leadership skills increase, management efficiency in secondary schools also improves.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between principals’ adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Pearson r on the Correlation between Principals’ Adaptability Skills and Management Efficiency

Source of Variation	N	r	Remark
Adaptability Skills	619	0.68	High Relationship
Management Efficiency			

Table 3 shows that there is a high positive relationship between principals’ adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is shown by the size of Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient r , which is 0.68.

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant relationship between principals’ interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson Correlation between Principals’ Interpersonal Skills and Management Efficiency

Source of Variation	N	r	p-value	Remark
Interpersonal Skills	619	0.71	0.00	Sig
Management Efficiency				

Analysis on Table 4 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals’ interpersonal skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.71) had P -value < 0.05 . The 1st null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant relationship between principals’ leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of Significance of Pearson Correlation between Principals’ Leadership Skills and Management Efficiency

Source of Variation	N	r	p-value	Remark
Leadership Skills	619	0.76	0.00	Sig
Management Efficiency				

Table 5 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals’ leadership skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.76) had P -value < 0.05 . The 2nd null hypothesis was therefore rejected. The result is statistically significant, suggesting that leadership competencies such as vision sharing, delegation, ethical conduct, and staff development strongly influence efficient school management.

Hypothesis 3: There will be no significant relationship between principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of Significance of Pearson Correlation between Principals' Adaptability Skills and Management Efficiency

Source of Variation	N	r	p-value	Remark
Adaptability Skills				
Management Efficiency	619	0.68	0.00	Sig

Table 6 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.68) had P -value < 0.05 . The 3rd null hypothesis was therefore rejected. The significant p -value indicates that principals who adjust effectively to policy changes, technological innovations and crises manage schools more efficiently.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed a high positive relationship between principals' interpersonal skills and management efficiency in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that as principals demonstrate stronger interpersonal skills such as effective communication, empathy, trust-building and teamwork, the efficiency of school management improves. The rejection of the null hypothesis indicates that interpersonal skills are critical determinants of how effectively principals manage human and material resources, maintain discipline and coordinate school activities.

This finding aligns strongly with Olorisade and Olaoluwa (2024), who found that principals' interpersonal skills were rated highly and played an important role in shaping teacher morale and school outcomes. Although their study reported that interpersonal skills did not significantly influence teacher morale, the present study extends the understanding by showing that interpersonal skills significantly enhance management efficiency, especially in the Nigerian secondary school context.

The finding also supports Ofojebe and Akudo (2021), who established a strong correlation between interpersonal skills and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State. Since teacher performance is a core component of school management efficiency, the present study confirms that principals' interpersonal competence contributes to better coordination, supervision and productivity. Similarly, the result is consistent with Akporehe and Asiyai (2023), who reported significant relationships between principals' human relations skills and teachers' job performance in Delta State. The agreement between the two studies suggests that interpersonal skills are universally important across different states in Nigeria for enhancing administrative effectiveness.

Furthermore, the finding agrees with Nambe, Agbulu and Odeh (2024), who found that principals' conflict resolution and staff appraisal skills significantly impacted effective administration in Benue State. Conflict resolution is a key interpersonal skill, and its effectiveness contributes directly to management efficiency, thereby reinforcing the present study's conclusion. The finding of the corresponding hypothesis shows a significant relationship between principals' interpersonal skills and management efficiency in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

The finding showed that there is a high positive relationship between leadership skills management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. This indicates that principals who communicate vision clearly, delegate responsibilities, motivate staff, model ethical behavior, and provide instructional leadership tend to manage schools more efficiently. This finding is in agreement with Aondona (2019), who found that principals' leadership effectiveness significantly impacted school management in areas such as supervision, communication, decision-making, discipline and community relations. The present study confirms that leadership competence remains a strong predictor of management efficiency in contemporary school administration.

The result also aligns with Busa, Garba and Ekpo (2023), who reported that principals' leadership skills significantly influenced teachers' job performance in Katsina State. Since teachers' job performance is central to school effectiveness, the present study extends their findings by showing that leadership skills also enhance overall management efficiency. In addition, the finding supports Kenayathulla and Hoque (2021), who found that effective principal leadership practices predicted school effectiveness in Niger State. Their use of multiple regression to predict school effectiveness complements the present study's correlational evidence, suggesting a consistent pattern across Nigerian states. The finding further agrees with Ajimi (2024), who found that visionary, ethical, and crisis leadership were dominant traits among principals in Saudi Arabia. Although the context differs, both studies underscore the importance of leadership skills in achieving educational goals and managing schools effectively. The finding of the corresponding hypothesis showed that the relationship between principals' leadership skills management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State was significant.

The finding revealed a positive relationship between principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. This implies that principals who can adjust to policy changes, technological innovations, crises and unexpected challenges are more efficient in managing their schools. This finding aligns with Alene, Tsegaye and Wolle (2025), who found that adaptive leadership practices helped principals in Ethiopia to address complex educational challenges and quality crises. The present study supports their conclusion by showing that adaptability enhances efficient school management. The result is also consistent with Sumiati et al. (2024), who found that adaptive leadership significantly influenced teacher performance in Indonesia, with collaborative school culture as a mediator. Since teacher performance contributes to management efficiency, the present study strengthens the argument that adaptability is a key leadership competence.

Furthermore, the finding agrees with Saputra and Hidayati (2024), whose ethnographic study showed that principals' ability to set direction, develop people and redesign organizations enhanced school resilience and effectiveness. The present study quantitatively confirms that adaptability contributes to efficient administration. The result also resonates with Malco (2024), who found that leadership competencies and resilience jointly enhanced organizational performance and governance. Adaptability, being a component of leadership competence, therefore plays a crucial role in effective school management. The corresponding hypothesis shows that the relationship between principals' adaptability skills and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State was significant.

Conclusion

The findings of the study showed that there is a positive and significant relationship existing between principals' soft skills (interpersonal, leadership and adaptability) and management efficiency in secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that principals' soft skills interpersonal, leadership and adaptability skills are critical determinants of management efficiency in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Therefore, improving principals' soft skills is a strategic pathway to enhancing management efficiency and achieving educational goals in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and educational implications, the study recommends:

1. Principals should be trained on advanced interpersonal and leadership skills to promote collaboration and ethical management in schools.
2. School administrators should develop adaptive leadership and resilience strategies to effectively navigate reforms and crises.
3. Principals should engage teachers and stakeholders in participatory decision-making processes to enhance trust, transparency and efficiency.

References

- Umeghalu, E. O. and Obi, C. E. (2020). New teachers' soft skills and productivity in senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education*, 7(1), 136-155.
- Saputra, H. Y. and Hidayati, D. (2024). The role of principal leadership in developing levels of resilience: A private senior secondary school ethnographic study. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 18(4), 1486-1494.
- Sumiati, D. A., Kurniady, D. A., Komariah, A., Suryana, A., Dadi. and Hafidh, Z. (2024). Linking principal adaptive leadership to teacher performance: The mediating effect of collaborative school culture. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*, 15(4), 17-41.

- Olorisade, O. G. and Olaoluwa, T. T. (2024). Principals' interpersonal skills teachers' morale and students' academic performance in secondary schools. *Al-Tanzim Journal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 8(4), 1083-1096.
- Olayemi, F. S. (2023). Building emotional intelligence and soft skills. <https://ng.linkedin.com/in/folasayo-samuel-olayemi-57955b148>
- Okeke and Ugwoke (2021) assert that school management efficiency requires the principal to combine technical competence with emotional and interpersonal sensitivity to drive performance and motivation among staff.
- Ofojebe, W. N. and Akudo, F. U. (2021). Interpersonal skills as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Awka education zone of Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*, 9.
- Ogbonnaya N.O. (2019). *Foundations of Education Finance 2nd Ed*. Nsukka: Hall Publishers. P. 15.
- Nworgu, B.G. (2015). *Educational research. Basic issues and methodology*. Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.
- Northouse, P.G. (2019). *Leadership: Theory and practice*. Sage Publications.
- Nurhattati, Rahmawati, D., Rugaiyah, Ripki, A. J. H. and Wicaksono, D. (2023). The adaptability of school principal and teachers in curriculum design and lesson plan at COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 12(2), 1097-1104.
- Nwachukwu, I. O. and Ezeani, C. E. (2022). Adolescence, learning, and national development: The significance of secondary education. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Management*, 14(1), 88–103.
- Nwaelehia, P. C., Woken, J. C. and Orji, U. W. (2024). Principals' management and organization skills for the administration of secondary schools in Rivers State. *International Journal of Innovative Social and Science Education Research*, 12(3), 198 – 205.
- Nambbe, A., Agbulu, C. A. and Odeh, R. C. (2024). Impact of principals' managerial skills on effective administration of public secondary schools in Benue State. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 5(10), 2543-2551.
- Martin, A. J., Nejad, H. G., Colmar, S. and Liem, G. A. D. (2020). Adaptability: How students' responses to uncertainty and novelty predict their academic and non-academic outcomes. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 112(4), 764–778. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000390>.
- Malco, J. M. E. (2024). Leadership competencies and resiliencies of school administrators: Basis for improved organizational performance and governance. In Guild of Educators in Tesol *International Research Journal*, 2(4), 174-302. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14293449>.
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A. and Hopkins, D. (2020). Seven strong claims about successful school leadership revisited. *School Leadership and Management*, 40(1), 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2019.1596077>
- Kamalu, S. I. and Mbakwe, V. C. (2022). Analysis of soft skills among secondary teachers in Rivers State. *Journal of Education and Society*, 12(2), 2545-2554.
- Kenayathulla, H. B. and Hoque, K. E. (2021). Principal leadership practices and school effectiveness in Niger State, Nigeria. *South African Journal of Education*, 41(3), 1859-1870.

- Hallinger, P. and Heck, R. H. (2021). Collaborative leadership and school improvement: understanding the impact on school capacity and student learning. *School Leadership and Management*, 30(2), 95–110.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). *National policy on education (6th edition)*.
- Gertrude, O. I., Ahiwe, N, E. C. and Obinna, O. (2023). Teacher soft skills and students' performance in public secondary schools in Abia State: The problem-solving strategy. *NAEAP Journal of Studies in Educational Administration and management*, 1(1), 283-291.
- Ogheneakoke, E. C., Ukor, O. D., Obro, S., Sharma, S. N., & Akpochofo, W. P. (2025). Utilisation of Social Network Sites and Social Studies Undergraduates' Scholarly Performance. *St. Theresa Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 11(2), 178-191. <https://doi.org/10.26643/edu/1>
- Busa, A. I., Garba, S. W. and Ekpo, P. O. (2023). Principals' leadership skills and teachers' job performance of senior secondary schools in Dutsin-Ma local government area of Kastina State, Nigeria.
- Aondona, S. I. (2019). *Principals' leadership effectiveness and the management of public secondary schools in North Central Nigeria*. Thesis submitted to Post Graduate School, Benue State University, Makurdi.
- Alene, A. A., Tsegaye, M. A. and Wolle, G. S. (2025). Secondary school principals' adaptive leadership practices amid the quality education crisis in Amhara regional state, Ethiopia. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101349>.
- Akporehe, D. A. and Asiyai, R. I. (2023). Principals' managerial skills and teachers' job performance: Evidence from public secondary schools in Delta State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 4(3), 78–84. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2023.4.3.591>.
- Ajmi, H. R. A. (2024). Principals' leadership skills to meet the national strategy for education in basic schools. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 11(2), 413–421.